

PROCESSING XBT CASSETTES FROM THE NOAA SHIPBOARD
ENVIRONMENTAL DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM (SEAS)

Philip Hadsell and Darrel Knoll

National Oceanographic Data Center
NOAA/NESDIS
Washington, D.C. 20235

ABSTRACT

NOAA's Shipboard Environmental Data Acquisition System (SEAS) has proven to be a reliable and economical system for acquiring digital XBT data at sea and transmitting it via satellite to operational centers and other real-time users. The high resolution profiles captured on the Hewlett Packard digital cassette tapes also offer the delayed-mode user with relatively inexpensive and rapid access to these data. The National Oceanographic Data Center has recently developed a processing system for XBT data recorded on SEAS cassette tapes. This system builds on and incorporates features of NODC's analog XBT temperature profile processing system, but accommodates special features and requirements of the cassette tapes.

end points ("flexure points") of these line segments became the archived depth-temperature pairs.

The processing of XBT strip charts involved considerable human intervention. During prescreening of the analog strip charts, traces were annotated to indicate where to start and stop the digitization process. Traces with excessive noise due to wire breaks or leakages were rejected outright. In addition, the prescreening and digitization process enabled NODC staff to identify potential problems such as excessive slopes, positive gradients, and cases where the probe hit bottom, and to take the necessary corrective action. With digital cassettes, however, there is no comparable graphic picture of the data readily available for review prior to reading and processing the digital cassette.

INTRODUCTION

Since it was developed nearly 25 years ago by the Sippican Corporation, the expendable bathythermograph (XBT) system relied on strip chart recorders to capture ocean temperature profiles as analog "traces". Now, however, this mode of operation is being superseded by direct digital recording of data on cassette tapes. In the late 1960's, in cooperation with the U.S. Navy Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center (FNOC), the National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) developed a system for digitizing, quality controlling, and archiving XBT data. Since that time over 700,000 XBTs have been digitized by NODC, FNOC, and private contractors. These digital data have accumulated in an NODC archive file where they are available to researchers around the world. To accommodate XBT data on digital cassettes, NODC has adapted its processing procedures and developed a system for handling them.

In the most recent version of its XBT processing system, NODC used a digitizer that converted horizontal or vertical movement of the stylus along the analog trace to depth and temperature values. The 0.005 inch resolution of the digitizer equates to a depth and temperature resolution of 0.5 m and 0.05 °C. From this analog-to-digital (A-D) output a series of line segments were fitted to the data such that no individual point deviated from the line by more than 0.015 inches or 0.15°C. The

SHIPBOARD ENVIRONMENTAL DATA
ACQUISITION SYSTEM

NOAA's Shipboard Environmental Data Acquisition System (SEAS) program augments and expands NOAA's collection of oceanographic and marine weather data.[1] SEAS is a highly portable shipboard automated station that accurately and quickly receives, stores, and transmits (via GOES satellites) meteorological and oceanographic data. The semi-automatic system is based on a Hewlett Packard HP-85 microcomputer. An XBT controller interfaces the XBT launcher and the HP-85. This system automatically records on cassette tape the digital voltages representing temperature values and processes each XBT drop for real-time transmission to NOAA's National Environmental Satellite, Data, and Information Service (NESDIS). Figure 1 depicts the SEAS Real-Time Data Routing.

At the present time there are approximately 50 semi-automatic SEAS systems deployed on NOAA ships and participating ships of opportunity. There are two types of semi-automatic SEAS systems. Each has somewhat different characteristics attributable to the respective system design contractors, Bath Systems, Inc. and Suttron Systems, Inc. With respect to XBT data processing, the most significant difference between these two systems is the format of the digital cassette tapes they produce. The Suttron and Bath systems record DC voltages. The values are recorded for specific

Figure 1 Path of SEAS Data Delivery

time intervals (0.1 s), which is approximately equivalent to 0.6 m (based on the known free fall rate of the XBT probe). The raw data and the associated position, date, and time information are stored on cassette tapes. Each cassette can store data from approximately 30 XBT drops.

CASSETTE DATA PROCESSING CYCLE

Acquisition

When SEAS cassettes are received at NODC, they -- along with other types of data -- enter the NODC Data Entry System. The data shipment is entered into the automated Data Entry Tracking System which records information on who submitted the data, when the data was collected, where the data was collected, and how much data was collected. The system assigns NODC reference numbers and produces an acknowledgement letter that is sent to the submitter to verify that the data was received. An inventory transaction record is automatically generated to update the NODC inventory system.

Conversion

The process of converting XBT data to NODC's archival storage format begins when the data values are transferred from the cassette to NODC's in-house VAX 11/750. This is done using a program written in HP-85 BASIC via a direct serial I/O connection to the VAX. The operator loads the appropriate transfer program (Bathy or Suttron) on the NODC HP-85 and inserts the data cassette. The program prompts the operator for the names of the files that are on the data cassette. The operator

enters the names of the files that are to be transferred and then logs onto the VAX on an adjacent terminal. Two devices (the HP-85 and a VAX terminal) are required when transferring the data because the HP-85 is not running under a communications protocol. The HP-85 simply sends the data down the wire. In order for the VAX to receive the data and write them to a disk file an interactive session must be initiated. After this session has been established, the operator tells the HP-85 to begin sending the files. The HP-85 opens the first cassette file, transfers the data, closes that cassette file, opens the next file, and continues until all cassette files have been transferred. At this point the operator can either close the VAX file or, if there is a second tape for the same cruise, enter the list of file names and have data from that tape included in the same VAX file. When all of the data for a cruise have been transferred, the VAX file is closed and the HP-85 program terminates.

NODC purposely limited its HP-85 function to data transfer in anticipation that the next generation of SEAS equipment will probably not use the HP-85, but some other processor recording on some other medium. Most of the VAX software will probably be applicable for some time to come.

The next step is to convert the raw data to a modified version of NODC's Universal Bathythermograph (UBT) format. There is a separate conversion program for data recorded by the Bathy and Suttron systems because of the fundamental differences between the raw data files. The VAX file that is generated by the Bathy transfer program contains a Julian date that must be translated to

year/month/day form. The raw Bathy data does not contain a depth-to-bottom or cut-off depth, so the operator must construct a bottom depth file using information from the log sheet. This allows the conversion program to cut off the trace if the probe hit bottom. The raw Bathy representation of temperature and depth is a series of voltages that were recorded every tenth of a second. The program converts the voltages to temperature values and applies the appropriate algorithm for the probe type to convert times into depth values. The raw Suttron data that are transferred to the VAX have already had the voltages converted to temperatures so the conversion program only has to convert the times to depths. The Suttron record carries date in year/month/day form so it does not have to be converted, and the data contains a cut-off depth that the conversion program can use.

The converted data are written to a disk file in the modified UBT format. These records contain all of the NODC codes, flags, etc., that are included in a UBT record, but all of the raw depth-temperature values are present instead of a smaller number of flexure points, and the depths are to tenths of meters (instead of whole meters). These records can contain up to 3200 depth-temperature pairs. At this point the data are in a common format regardless of the recording system that was used. The UBT data record does contain information, however, that identifies the source as a cassette from either a Bathy or a Suttron system.

The next operation is the real data processing step; everything up to this point is done to prepare the data for processing. The next program removes spikes, smooths the "trace", and calculates the flexure points that will be stored to describe the trace. The output from this program is an actual NODC UBT record that contains header information and a series of up to 305 depth-temperature pairs with depths to whole meters and temperatures to hundredths of a degree Celsius. The technical details of this program will be described later.

Quality Assurance and Archiving

The data are now ready to be transferred to the NODC data archives, which are maintained on a mainframe system (Sperry 1100 series) located at the National Climatic Data Center (NCDC), Asheville, N.C. Here the data are subject to the same quality assurance testing as data that were digitized from strip charts. The UBT records are segmented into 80-character pieces and transmitted to the Sperry mainframe via a communications line using 3780 bisync protocol. There the pieces are reassembled into a file of UBT records. The quality assurance group is notified that the data are available. After the data pass through this system and are verified as "clean", they are added to the monthly transaction tape that is passed to the data archiving group. During the next XBT update cycle, the data will be added to the NODC XBT archive file and the inventory will be updated to reflect the presence of these data.

After the data have been successfully transferred to the quality assurance group, there is a certain amount of cleanup work that must be performed on the VAX. The files of "raw" pseudo-UBT data are converted to a character format and written to tape. These data will be retained and available from NODC for several years. Once the tape copies have been made, all disk files that were used to process these data are deleted and the original cassettes are sent to the SEAS office to be recycled.

DATA PROCESSING

In an attempt to obtain the best digital product with the minimum amount of resources, NODC developed several variations to the basic processing system using the preprocessed XBT file. Initially we accepted the preprocessed XBT observations and continued our normal activity of reducing the number of depth-temperature pairs to flexure points using the same criteria NODC uses in analog XBT processing. Before long, however, we realized that there were a significant number of temperature spikes in the original data that were being selected as flexure points for NODC's archives.*

Attempts were made to smooth the original digital profile using least squares curve fitting. This option was rejected because it resulted in interpolated depth-temperature pairs. However, NODC will be investigating similar techniques for future applications.

SPIKE IDENTIFICATION

The mechanism to automatically identify excessive temperature gradients (spikes) using the NODC VAX 11/750 becomes difficult without the benefit of human analysis. This is especially true when the magnitude of the spike is borderline to the physical characteristics of the ocean. NODC selected 2°C/m as the maximum temperature gradient permitted. In doing so we realize that valid temperature differences between adjacent depth levels of less than 1 meter may translate to gradients exceeding 2°C/m. This physical characteristic only occurs in relatively small areas of the ocean, however, usually associated with oceanic fronts. Increasing our spike window would introduce much more suspect data into the XBT archives and create problems for the subsequent data users.

The test for temperature spikes assumes that the starting surface temperature value is valid. In NODC's development activity we found this not to be true in a few cases, resulting in subsequent valid depth-temperature pairs being removed. The review of the raw data clearly showed the first two temperatures well outside those comprising the

* Flexure point selection for the real-time transmission of XBT data may also contain temperature spikes. These data are also manually edited at NOAA's National Meteorological Center before being routed through the GTS network.

isothermal layer. In consultation with NOS SEAS Project personnel NODC was advised that the first four or five depth temperature pairs should be discarded because of the time response of the XBT probe thermistor.[2] This is equivalent to the elimination of all temperature values in the first 3 m. Since there is no surface (0 m) temperature value present, the temperature value at 3 m is used to create the surface depth-temperature pair.

SPIKE TESTING AND REMOVAL

Starting with the 5th depth-temperature pair (~3 m), the digital XBT record is evaluated for temperature spikes exceeding 2°C/m. If

$$\left| \frac{T_n - T_{n+1}}{D_n - D_{n+1}} \right| > 2^\circ\text{C/m}$$

then temperature T_{n+1} is eliminated. At this point in the evaluation we do not know if the depth-temperature pair (D_{n+1}, T_{n+1}) was an isolated spike, the beginning of a large thermocline, or the beginning of a major failure such as a wire break. If this is an isolated spike, one would expect the next temperature value T_{n+2} to be close to the T_n value. The test for this condition is

$$\left| \frac{T_n - T_{n+2}}{D_n - D_{n+2}} \right| < 0.3^\circ\text{C/m}$$

If three successive levels, $D_{n+1}, D_{n+2}, D_{n+3}$, have gradients exceeding 2°C/m, the profile is cut off at (D_n, T_n) . If the gradient for the next temperature value T_{n+2} is within 2°C/m, but not within 0.3°C/m, or if $(T_{n+2} - T_{n+3})$ is not positive, (D_{n+2}, T_{n+2}) is also deleted. This process continues for 10 successive depth-temperature pairs. When the condition is true, 'n' is incremented to the depth-temperature pair that satisfied the criteria. If the criterion is not met after 10 successive pairs, the profile is cut off at D_n, T_n . The test for positive temperature differences was instituted to retain the profile at large thermoclines (Figure 2).

FLEXURE POINT COMPUTATION

After spikes are removed from the profile, the data are compressed to flexure points by fitting a series of line segments such that no depth-temperature pair deviates from the line segment by more than 0.1°C. The end points of these line segments are saved. The flexure point window of 0.1°C is smaller than that used in processing the analog traces (0.15°C). The rationale for this change is based upon the digitization method for the data. It is felt that the A-D process used for data from the SEAS system is more precise than that of the manual following of the analog trace with the stylus of the digitizer equipment. A

Figure 2 Typical Spikes found in Cassette XBT

Figure 3 SEAS Cassette XBT

plot showing the raw data (dotted line) and the flexure points (X's) is depicted in Figure 3.

FORMAT CONVERSION

Next the compressed SEAS profile is converted to the NODC processing and archive format. Because NODC's archive format calls for the depth values to be in whole meters, the depth values are rounded and evaluated for adjacent duplicate depths. If a duplicate depth is found, the second

one and its corresponding temperature value is deleted. The final step is to smooth the data by retaining only the end points of isothermal layers. An isothermal layer is defined as one with all adjacent temperatures within 0.05°C of each other.

DISCUSSION

To date NODC has processed approximately 40 XBT cassette tapes. The system has performed extremely well, but careful review of the final product is still required to identify more subtle malfunctions. Profile characteristics such as straight isothermal profiles from some type of short circuit or positive gradients from wire stretch cannot be caught automatically at this time and require human intervention.

To ensure data compatibility NODC welcomes the opportunity to compare results obtained with its system to those of other institutions. Interested persons are invited to contact the authors at the NODC. Limited comparisons have been made with a cassette tape processed at the NOAA Atlantic Meteorological and Oceanographic Laboratory (AOML) (with spikes removed manually) and also processed at NODC using the procedures described in this paper. The major difference between the two outputs was the number of flexure points retained: the AOML version had approximately 10 percent more points.

REFERENCES

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